

Dendrochronological analysis of timber from Gammel Strand, Copenhagen.

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Over three years, from 2013 to 2016, samples from timbers from the archaeological excavation at Gammel Strand in Copenhagen have been analysed dendrochronologically. The excavations were carried out by Københavns Museum in connection with Metro Cityring project, with Stuart Whatley as the excavation leader. The dendrochronological analysis was carried out to enable the precise dating of the felling of the trees used in a series of large quayside constructions and to determine the region where these trees had grown. This analysis thus has provided details of the chronology of the many constructions that were established over several centuries at the site and has allowed insight into the changes in trade of timber to Copenhagen through the post-Medieval period, both in terms of timber type (genus) and source region.

A total of 366 samples were submitted for analysis. Some of these were not analysed however, often when they contained less than c. 40 rings. Others were reserved for later analysis if necessary, on the basis of results as they emerged. A number of these remain not analysed. In all then, 320 samples were analysed. A total of 108 of the analysed samples could not be dated. Of the oak, 122 samples are dated and 11 not. For the pines 81 are dated while 86 could not be dated. And 9 of the 20 spruce samples could be dated (see fig 1).

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Fig. 1. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen. Summary of the material in terms of numbers of dated vs undated samples.

It is noteworthy to mention that the success rate for dating this material is quite good for what is often expected of Danish material. A success rate of 90% has been seen for oaks, and here the results at Gammel Strand follow suit. In Denmark where pines were imported in the Post-medieval period a successful dendrochronological dating of just 30% of samples can occur, so the 48% of samples dated here is a good result. In regions where pine is native, a much more successful rate is normal (e.g. some years ago all 25 pine samples from the Barcode site in Oslo could be dated (Daly 2008c)). Equally, 45% of the spruce samples from Gammel Strand are successfully dated.

Methodology

The science of dendrochronology is described extensively elsewhere so this will not be described in extensive detail here (Baillie 1982; 1995; Hillam 1998; Daly 2007a). The method utilised the phenomenon that trees, as they grow, form an annual ring. The width of the ring is strongly influenced by the climate affecting the tree, so that two trees growing at the same time, in the same region will display very similar growth, as reflected in the variation, year by year, in their ring width. By measuring the rings widths along an old tree's growth, across the cross-section of a timber, it is possible to compare trees to each other, and find where they cross-match. Due to extensive tree-ring datasets that have been built across Europe by colleagues over the last 50 years or so, it is now possible to compare timbers of unknown age to a range of regional chronologies and precisely date these.

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Also, as the climate signal preserved in timber is to a large extent region-specific, the method can also be used to identify the region of origin of the timber, so-called provenance determination.

In order to carry out the analysis of timbers from Gammel Strand slices through chosen timbers were taken with a chain saw. The criteria for identifying suitable timbers included choosing ones with bark or bark-edge preserved so that the dating of the actual felling year of the tree would be achieved. It was also important to choose timbers with at least 50 rings, usually more, to maximise the possibility of achieving successful dating results. Also, other timbers without sapwood or bark preserved were selected from each construction to enable insight into the timber procurement for each extensive structure. Of course, timbers from all phases that were observed archaeologically were selected, to achieve full detail of the chronology of building activity on the site, and to identify repairs and maintenance to structures over time.

In the laboratory the samples are prepared by paring on the cross-section to expose the tree-rings from the innermost to the outermost ring. The ring widths are then measured using a measuring stage under a stereo microscope and the tree-ring data is analysed using a program "DENDRO" (Tyers 1997) designed for dealing with tree-ring analysis. Correlation between tree-ring datasets is calculated using t-test ("CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher 1973)). Tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe, generated by researchers from a range of laboratories, are consulted in the analysis, and the sources of these are given in the tables below.

The results of the analysis are presented here divided into the main archaeological construction contexts identified archaeologically. In some instances, it is the dendrochronological dating that has identified which structure a timber belonged, but for the most part the dendrochronology confirmed the timber's assignment to the archaeological context identified. The construction phases were given colour designations to allow clarity, and I have chosen to retain these colours in the plans, as this system helps hugely in understanding the chronology of site.

Phase 1

Fig. 2. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 1. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

Fig. 3. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, bulwerk G656, Phase 1. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

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Bulwark G656

The timbers giving the earliest dating on the Gammel Strand site are from Phase 1. This consisted of timbers under a stone wall and an east-west running bulwark. The dating of the samples from this phase is illustrated in fig. 2. All the samples analysed are oak and all could be dated. Three of the eight samples from the timbers under the wall have sapwood preserved, and one of these has bark edge also. The sample with bark edge is from a tree that was felled in winter AD 1531-32. Nine of the 15 samples from the Phase 1 bulwark G656 have sapwood. Four of these have complete sapwood to bark edge preserved and the results show that these four are all from trees felled in winter 1532-33. The trees for the wall foundation, however, might all have been felled a year earlier than those of the Phase 1 bulwark (G656). There is one example in this group where the results suggest that two timbers are from the same tree.

In fig. 3 the position of the structure that belongs to this dated phase is shown.

Table 1. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 1. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. [See full table in Appendix 1](#)

The results of the correlation of the tree-ring curves from Phase 1 suggest that the timbers are harvested from the same region, in that the agreements between the samples suggest a very homogeneous group (table 1). The reason one timber does not display very high agreement is because this sample contains only 47 rings. Twenty-two tree-ring series, representing 21 trees, are averaged to form a mean curve (B027oak B purple) 285 years in length, spanning the period AD 1248-1532. The curve is dating with a wide range of tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe and achieves highest correlation with a wide variety of master and site chronologies for southern Scandinavia. By the 16th century in southern Scandinavia extensive trade in oak as a building material takes place, so that the oak tree-ring dataset for the region is a complicated mixture of local and imported material. The Phase 1 timbers achieve very high correlation ($t = 17.91$) with tree-ring data from a shipwreck Klippan 2 built c. AD 1540 from Göteborg (Daly 2015c) and with timbers from an altarpiece at Seville Cathedral built AD 1549-54 ($t = 14.80$) (Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015). Dendrochronological provenance determination has shown that both these structures are made from oaks that grew in west Sweden. The west Swedish region is likely to be the source for the oaks used in Phase 1 bulwark at Gammel Strand.

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Filenames	-	-	B027oak B purple	B027oak C orange	
-	start	dates	AD1248	AD1331	
-	dates	end	AD1532	AD1557	
Master chronologies					
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	11,72	12,90	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	12,44	13,22	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
2M000006	AD1318	AD1514	11,75	11,93	Sjælland kirker (Daly e.g. 1998b&c)
LS10BM01	AD1413	AD1509	9,06	6,21	Löddeköp torn 2 timbers (Lund Uni revised Daly 2007a)
O0370009	AD1350	AD1430	8,92	9,44	Landskrona (Bartholin pers comm)
O0800009	AD1301	AD1561	8,84	6,34	Halmstad (Bartholin pers comm)
SM000004	AD1198	AD1495	8,33	5,40	Skåne (Lund University)
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	10,48	10,31	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001b)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	9,56	12,61	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
2119M001	AD1361	AD1471	8,57	8,38	Ejby K. 9 timbers (Daly 1998c)
SM100003	AD1135	AD1711	8,22	8,51	Ystad area (Lund University)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	8,02	7,72	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
2136M001	AD1360	AD1473	7,88	9,12	Næstved. Det Gamle Rådhus (Daly 2000c)
8104M002	AD1371	AD1412	5,49	8,09	Understed K. 3 timbers (Daly 1998d)
shipwrecks					
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	17,91	15,60	Klippan 2 shipwreck Göteborg 11 timbers (Daly 2015c)
Z027M002	AD1313	AD1567	11,49	8,65	Amager Strand ship 9 timbers (Daly 2008a)
bispevika09&12	AD1365	AD1539	9,77	12,56	Bispevika 09 & 12 ships Oslo 2 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	9,75	13,02	Gåsehage Randers 2 timbers (Daly 2009)
Z073m001	AD1385	AD1574	9,04	14,70	Oslo Barcode ship 14 3 timbers (Daly 2011e)
Z147M002	AD1363	AD1535	7,61	10,82	Bispevika 4 ship Oslo B3B7 5 timbers (Daly 2016g)
Z089m001	AD1399	AD1581	6,07	12,06	Oslo Barcode skib 5. 9 timbers (Daly 2013a)
Z064M001	AD1313	AD1481	7,23	8,62	Oslo Sørenga 9 3 timbers (Daly 2011c)

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Z171M001	AD1400	AD1548	8,06	6,26	Bispevika 3 ship Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2016f)
Timber imports from West Sweden(?)					
q415029m04	AD1356	AD1540	14,80	13,94	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral 29 planks (Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015)
D014M001	AD1319	AD1521	13,60	9,59	Nørregade Odense Gråbrødre klostres baghave 2 timbers (Daly 2015a)
B012M001	AD1347	AD1484	11,18	9,82	Admiralgade Copenhagen 3 timbers (Daly 2005)
2117M001	AD1316	AD1514	10,56	9,24	Hammer K. 5 trees (Daly 1998b)
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	10,49	13,33	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013g)
81M00004	AD1350	AD1480	10,28	13,94	kirker i Vendsyssel W Sweden group 24 timber (Daly 1998g)
8111M001	AD1350	AD1480	10,01	14,86	Astrup K. 13 timbers (Daly 1998e)
CD839Z01	AD1366	AD1511	10,49	7,71	Sulsted kirke 4 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007a)
4077M00X	AD1178	AD1546	7,25	12,16	Nyborg slot gruppe A & B 46 timber (Daly 1999)
8113M001	AD1350	AD1440	7,36	9,35	Mårup K. 9 timbers (Daly 1998f)
H011M001	AD1386	AD1563	6,85	9,90	Aalborg Algade Tiendeladen hus 4 timbers (Daly 2016d)
EDINCAS2	AD1358	AD1509	6,26	8,52	Edinburgh Castle 13 timbers (Crone pers comm)

Table 2. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 1 and Phase 2. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the mean curves from the datasets and diverse master and site chronologies.

Phase 2

Bulwark G602 and Phase 3 storm post group G646

There are 36 timbers that are assigned to the next bulwark phase, comprising bulwarks group G602 from Phase 2 and storm post group G646 from Phase 3. The phase consisted chiefly of an east-west running timber bulwark, of very closely spaced upright squared posts. Outside this alignment on the seaward side there are posts placed intermittently (see fig. 4).

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Fig. 4. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 2. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction. The Phase 2 bulwark represents G602 (in orange). The pink posts represent Phase 3 additions.

Of the 36 timbers analysed 32 are dated. All the samples from the main bulwark construction, 26 in all, are oak, while all those from the intermittent posts, the remaining 10, are of pine.

All the oak samples could be dated. Nine of these had sapwood preserved including four with bark edge. One timber with bark edge is from a tree felled in winter AD 1557-58 while the other three are from trees felled in spring/summer AD 1558 (fig. 5). Six of the ten pine samples could be dated. Three of these had bark edge preserved, while the rest had possible bark edge. Sapwood is not recorded on the conifer samples as the boundary between heartwood and sapwood on these is often difficult to identify with certainty, and because the number of sapwood rings in conifers can vary so greatly that it is not useful to use sapwood statistics to estimate the felling date for the trees, even where sapwood is recorded. The majority of the pines for the additional posts added to the Phase 2 bulwark G602 were felled in winter AD 1642-43, and were registered as storm post group G642. Clearly these are later additions to this structure.

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Fig. 5. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, bulwark G602 oaks (Phase 2) and storm post group G642 (Phase 3). Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

As can be seen in the table of internal correlation for the samples from the Phase 2 bulwark (table 3), 23 of the oaks cross-date well together, forming a homogeneous group. These 23 tree-ring curves are averaged to a mean (B027oak C G602) of 227 years long. This mean is dated with reference to oak tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe but achieves highest correlation with data from Southern Scandinavia (table 2), indicating a similar provenance for this timber as for the Phase 1 timber (described above). The mean curves for the oaks from the Phase 2 and Phase 1 match each other also, with a *t*-value of 13.11. The results suggest that the timber source for these two phases, felled in 1532 and 1558 respectively, is very similar, in the West Swedish region.

It is difficult to be so specific about the provenance of the three oaks that are not included in the homogeneous group. As can be seen in table 3, they are dating against some trees in the Phase 2 oak group, but when compared with Northern European datasets they show agreement with a range of Southern Scandinavian master and site chronologies. These three are from trees that grew in Southern Scandinavia, but it is not possible to be more specific.

The pines however produce a very clear indication of their timber origin. A clear homogeneous group is identified (table 3) and a mean (B027pine C G646) is made which is 159 years long. This mean is dating using tree-ring datasets for pine for Northern Europe

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but achieves clearly the highest correlation with data from Oslo in Norway (table 4). The remaining dated pine sample falls outside the group, and its provenance is not clear.

Table 3. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 2. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values. See full table in Appendix 2

Filenames	-	-	B027 pine C orange	B027634a	
-	start	dates	AD1484	AD1489	
-	dates	end	AD1642	AD1629	
N0251M01	AD1434	AD1621	14,04	3,04	Oslo Bispevika B3/B7 46 timbers (Daly 2016e)
N007m005	AD1471	AD1622	13,31	3,46	Oslo Barcode 11-13 Bolværk 22 timbers (Daly 2008c)
Bispevika 2...	AD1308	AD1621	13,12	3,36	Bispevika 2 Oslo pines 72 timbers (Daly forthcoming)
k010301s	AD1395	AD1706	10,44	3,70	Gulfhäuser farmhouse Lower Saxony Swedish timber (Crone pers comm)
20000059	AD1488	AD1647	8,85	-	Oslo Revierstr (Bartholin pers comm)
FYRSVEN3	AD1353	AD1636	8,27	-	Svendborg imports (Bartholin pers comm)
IMPORTx8	AD1329	AD1671	8,09	-	Scotland pine imports 59 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z129M001 A8...	AD1586	AD1842	8,01	-	Deichman & Diagonalen Oslo 9 timbers (Daly 2016b)
NOMK0803	AD1345	AD1780	7,81	3,63	Norway Aust-Agder (Bartholin pers comm)
N022M001	AD1457	AD1595	7,44	4,36	Oslo DEG felt vest 7 timbers (Daly 2013b)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	7,30	4,20	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
FYRSVEN1	AD1513	AD1636	7,25	3,44	Svenborg Norwegian imports (Bartholin pers comm)
Swed_mal	AD1083	AD1992	6,76	-	Malardalen Gotland Sweden (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_STK	AD1127	AD1671	6,70	3,73	Stockholm/Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	6,10	-	SNorway ships 63 timbers OAK (Daly unpubl)
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	5,80	-	Copenhagen B&W grund 24 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
N029M001	AD1308	AD1545	5,54	3,18	Bispevika 2 laftekasse 26 timbers (Daly forthcoming)
FM00601A	AD1439	AD1984	5,42	-	SW Finland (Zetterberg pers comm)

Table 4. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, storm post group G646 pines. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the mean curves from the datasets and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Fig. 6. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 3 bulwarks and posts. Bulwark group G674 is in red, bulwark group G648 and, storm post groups G646 and G649 are in pink. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

Phase 3

Bulwark G674

A total of 18 samples were extracted from Phase 3 G674. The structure consists of a linear post and horizontally placed plank revetment at the west end of the site (fig 6). Samples of both posts and planking were taken, but five of the planks contained too few tree-rings for analysis and these were only examined to determine their wood genus. The first striking result of the analysis of this structure was that the vast majority of the timbers analysed are of spruce/larch, probably spruce (the two genus are difficult to distinguish anatomically). Twelve conifers from the structure were analysed and it was found that only one was of pine. Of these nine, most of which have bark edge preserved, could be dated. These are from trees felled in winter AD 1625-26 (fig. 7).

A single oak sample assigned also to the Phase 3 has sapwood and possible bark edge preserved. It is clearly from a later felling phase, dating to AD 1689-90.

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Fig. 7. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 3 G674. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

		B027410a	B0274089	B0274069	B0274099	B027412a	B0274139	B0274079	B0274059	B027414a	B027578a
Average B027spruce D red	B027410a	*	8,64	-	-	-	-	4,41	4,6	3,31	-
	B0274089	8,64	*	4,51	5,27	3,85	4,22	7,91	7,45	5,49	-
	B0274069	-	4,51	*	14,51	3,65	5,52	7,44	8,55	5,52	-
	B0274099	-	5,27	14,51	*	5,41	6,25	7,48	9,12	5,34	-
	B027412a	-	3,85	3,65	5,41	*	7,47	5,32	5,32	3,89	-
	B0274139	-	4,22	5,52	6,25	7,47	*	6,24	6,75	5,92	-
	B0274079	4,41	7,91	7,44	7,48	5,32	6,24	*	16,2	6,74	-
	B0274059	4,6	7,45	8,55	9,12	5,32	6,75	16,2	*	6,11	-
	B027414a	3,31	5,49	5,52	5,34	3,89	5,92	6,74	6,11	*	-
	B027578a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*

Table 5. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 3 G674. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, blue = spruce/larch. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

As can be seen from the table of internal correlation (table 5), the tree-ring curves from the spruce samples achieve good internal agreement indicating that they are from a very similar region, even perhaps from one forest. An average of the group (B027spruce D G674) is made, which is 94 years long. The material is dating with datasets for pine from Scandinavia (and with chronologies from England that are Scandinavian imports). Determining the provenance of conifers is not as straight-forward as with oaks, but the results might suggest an East Swedish origin for this spruce timber.

The single oak timber assigned to the bulwark was found further east in the excavation than the main bulwark G674 timbers. This timber is from a tree felled 64 years later than the spruce and as the table of correlation shows (table 7) is from a tree that grew in Southern Norway. It also achieves very high correlation with oaks from the later Phase 3 and Phase 4 building phases described below. And as will be shown, must belong to the same phase as the Phase 4A land ties from 1689-90.

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Filenames	-	-	B027spruce D red	
-	start	dates	AD1532	
-	dates	end	AD1625	
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	6,61	Gotland Pinus (Bartholin pers comm)
DANSON2	AD1545	AD1767	5,82	Danson House Bexley Kent (Tyers nee Groves pers comm)
SWED_STK	AD1127	AD1671	5,60	Stockholm/Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	5,56	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
30530010	AD1343	AD1669	5,42	Skeppsholmen 36 series (Eggertsson pers comm)
Tilbury2	AD1513	AD1670	4,65	Tilbury Fort Essex Picea (Tyers nee Groves pers comm)
20000059	AD1488	AD1647	4,44	Oslo Revierstr (Bartholin pers comm)
Rangr-P2	AD1551	AD1663	4,20	Rangers House Greenwich Park London (Tyers nee Groves pers comm)
B027pine E pink	AD1471	AD1639	4,19	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine pink 8 timbers (Daly this report)
SWED_AAL	AD1068	AD1827	4,13	Aaland Pinus (Bartholin pers comm)

Table 6. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 3 G674. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the mean curve from the red dataset and diverse master and site chronologies.

Filenames	-	-	B027578a	
-	start	dates	AD1546	
-	dates	end	AD1689	
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	10,12	SNorway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z010m001	AD1480	AD1727	9,69	Larvik 5 & 6 Norway 8 timbers (Daly 2007b)
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	9,65	Copenhagen B&W Grund 24 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
B027oak F green lt1	AD1483	AD1690	9,33	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak green lt1 9 timbers (Daly this report)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	9,27	Ålborg Østerå & Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
Z029m001	AD1583	AD1803	7,21	Orekilen ship Norway 2 timbers (Daly 2008b)
JUTLAND6	AD846	AD1793	7,20	Jutland 452 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z049m001	AD1622	AD1716	6,12	Kampedal 3 Ulvøysund Aust Agder båd 2 timbers (Daly 2010a)

Table 7. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 3 G674. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the tree-ring curve from the single oak sample from Phase 3 and diverse master and site chronologies.

Bulwark G648

Archaeologically bulwark G648 appeared very similar in construction to the G674 revetment, and was also situated at the west end of the excavation site (see plan fig. 6). However, in terms of the wood analysis and dendrochronological dating there are many differences. A total of 27 samples were taken from the structure of which all but one were analysed. Only two of the timbers examined are of spruce/larch. There are eight oaks and 17 pines. Five of the oaks are dated, while 14 pine are dated. The results of the

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dating of this phase are illustrated together with the results for the bulwark G674 (fig. 8). Even though there were many dated pine timbers from the bulwark G648 for which it could not be confirmed that bark edge was present, there is a distinct group whose outermost preserved ring lies at c. AD 1623 to 1625. These are all from horizontal planks in the waterfront structure. It is not impossible that these are dating to within the same years as the Phase 3 structure. Upright posts of pine are added in winter AD 1639-40 and oaks from trees felled in 1623-24, 1626-27 and even as late as 1664. If the G674 and G648 Phase 3 revetments were built at the same time, it is logical to suggest that G674 was built as an internal support for filling this portion of the coastline and was quickly embedded in fill, while the outer revetment, to the harbour side, remained exposed, and maintained over several decades.

Fig. 8. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, bulwarks G674 (red) and G648 (pink), Phase 3. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

The dated series from the bulwark groups G674 (pink) and G648 (red) and storm post groups G646 and G649 mirror each other as shown in table 8. Two (B0276049 & B027319a) might be from the same tree. Two others (B027620a & B0276239) might also be from one tree. An average of the pine group representing eight trees (B027pine E pink as indicated) is 169 years long. The pine pink group is dating with a range of chronologies for pine for Northern Europe, with highest correlation with regions around the upper Baltic but it is not possible to be more specific in terms of the timber provenance (table 9).

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The five oaks from the G648 bulwark can be grouped together also, as can be seen in table 8. The oak (B027578a) dating to 1689-90 is not included here, as it clearly belongs to a later phase. The average B027oak E pink is 349 years long. This average correlates best with tree-ring datasets for oak for Southern Scandinavia, and these oaks probably grew in Southern Norway (table 10).

Table 8. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, G674 and G648 bulwarks. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine, blue = spruce/larch. The grey tones highlight the high t-values. See full table in Appendix 3

Of the tree-ring series for pine that do not belong clearly in the B027pine E pink group, one (B0276259) is clearly correlating best with the pine chronology for the G646 pine group dating to 1642-3 (see above). The second (B0276069) doesn't achieve a correlation that allows a provenance to be suggested. The third (B0276719) might be from a similar source to B027pine E from G646.

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Filenames	-	-	B027604 &619 same tree	B027pine E pink	
-	start	dates	AD1446	AD1471	
-	dates	end	AD1624	AD1639	
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	5,15	9,25	Gotland Pinus (Bartholin pers comm)
30530010	AD1343	AD1669	4,53	8,24	Skeppsholmen; 36 series (Eggertsson pers comm)
O0720091	AD1369	AD1662	6,20	8,16	Nykoping; Biografen (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_STK	AD1127	AD1671	4,08	7,11	Stockholm/Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	4,46	7,11	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
Danson1	AD1489	AD1758	-	6,92	Danson House Bexley Kent (Groves pers comm)
SWED_AAL	AD1068	AD1827	-	6,60	Aaland Pinus (Bartholin pers comm)
21213M01	AD1493	AD1631	4,74	6,36	Suså Næstved 5 trees (Daly 2001b)
Swed_mal	AD1083	AD1992	4,39	6,18	Malardalen Gotland Sweden (Bartholin pers comm)
lat-vppt	AD1565	AD1668	-	5,95	Latvia Ventspils Castle tower (Zunde pers comm)
N007m005 short	AD1479	AD1622	-	5,85	Barcode 11-13 Oslo Bolværk 22 timbers (Daly 2008c)
NOMK0803	AD1345	AD1780	-	5,57	Aust-Agder (Bartholin pers comm)
LATV001	AD1445	AD1739	-	5,45	Dannenstern House Riga (Zunde pers comm)
FYRSVEN1	AD1513	AD1636	-	5,44	Svenborg-Norge (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_UP1	AD1031	AD1638	5,32	5,18	Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
006526M1	AD1357	AD1578	4,55	4,14	Copenhagen B&W wreck 2 (Daly 2000b)
2101XM01	AD1364	AD1863	3,43	4,00	B&W Grund pine 35 timbers (Daly 1997a&c)
JM11627t	AD1368	AD1587	4,30	3,83	London-Westminster 107 Jermyn St. (Groves pers comm)

Table 9. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, G648 bulwark. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curves from the pines from the G648 bulwark and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Filenames	-	-	B027oak E pink	
-	start	dates	AD1315	
-	dates	end	AD1663	
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	13,51	South Norway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z071m004	AD1304	AD1595	11,39	Oalo Barcode ship BC08 5 timbers (Daly 2011e)
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	10,12	Copenhagen B&W grund IMPORTS 24 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	9,94	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	9,69	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	9,07	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
B027oak F g...	AD1483	AD1690	8,57	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak F green lt1 9 timbers (Daly this report)
Z010m001	AD1480	AD1727	8,26	Larvik 5 & 6 Norway 8 timbers (Daly 2007b)
bispevika o...	AD1351	AD1539	8,20	Bispevika oak ships april 2016 9 timbers (Daly unpubl)
StSerfM001	AD1377	AD1511	7,90	St Serfs church Dysart IMPORTS 7 timbers (Crone pers comm)
EDINCAS2	AD1358	AD1509	7,86	Edinburgh Castle 13 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z109M001	AD1437	AD1597	7,85	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2013f)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	7,77	B&W Grund Vrag 2. 2 trees (Daly 1997b)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	7,69	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
DUNTARVI	AD1385	AD1529	7,60	Duntarvi Scotland IMPORTS 2 timbers (Crone pers comm)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	7,54	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	7,36	Klippan 2 shipwreck Göteborg 11 timbers (Daly 2015c)
Z096M002	AD1351	AD1517	7,33	Bispevika 2 3 timbers (Daly 2013d)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	7,32	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)

Table 10. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen,. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the oaks from the G648 bulwark and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Phase 4

Phase 4 is complex and is constructed over several decades. Description of the different phases is thus sub-divided as the dendrochronological results dictate – chronologically. These are Phase 4A land ties, Phase 4 bulwarks (comprising a livewell/fish storage box) and Phase 4B land ties.

Phase 4A land ties

This construction phase consists of a series of anchor beams, stretcher beams and posts that can be followed across the site from west to east, as illustrated in fig. 9. A total of 50 samples were taken from this phase and 41 were analysed dendrochronologically; 24 pine, 11 oaks and 6 spruce. Of the analysed samples 28 are dated, and these results are illustrated in fig. 10. The dating results show that these timbers are from two distinct felling phases. Oaks and pines were felled in early AD 1692 and around 1689-91. A group of pines belong to a later phase in the late 1720s. A single oak might also belong to this later phase, felled in the period AD 1730-44.

Fig. 9. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4A land ties, SG618 Live well and Phase 4 bulwark timbers.
Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the constructions.

As can be seen in table 13, a number of groups can be identified within the material from the Phase 4A land ties phase. All but one of the 1692 pines form one group (group 1) and the average of this B027pine F green It1 gr1 is 149 years long. Two other small groups can be identified for the later, AD 1726 pines, as indicated (B027pine F green It1 gr2 is 71 years long while B027217&232 same tree is 132 years long). Group 1 is dating with Norway and might be from trees that grew in Norway, without the results allowing

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a more specific provenance. The other pine groups do not readily show where they might come from (table 14).

Fig. 10. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4A land tie phase. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

Table 11. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values. See full table in Appendix 4.

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Filenames	-	-	B027pine F green lt1 gr1	B027pine F green lt1 gr2	B027217 &232 same tree	
-	start	dates	AD1544	AD1657	AD1595	
-	dates	end	AD1692	AD1727	AD1726	
Z129M001 A8...	AD1586	AD1842	6,46	-	-	Oslo Deichman & Diagonalen 9 timbers (Daly 2016b)
EIDEMMK2	AD1560	AD1954	6,17	-	-	Flesberg Norway (Eidem 1959)
21010M01	AD1491	AD1743	6,16	-	3,20	B&W grund 4 trees (Daly 1996)
N027M001	AD1609	AD1862	5,97	-	-	Opera 2000 Oslo 11 timbers (Daly 2016c)
30160009	AD1573	AD1764	5,96	-	-	Naes Herrgaard (Bartholin pers comm)
Oxpine	AD1440	AD1748	5,79	-	-	Norfolk Oxburgh Hall 7 timbers (Tyers pers comm)
Z149M001	AD1608	AD1749	5,77	-	-	Gullbranna pine ship Halland 2 timbers (Daly 2016a)
2101M001	AD1487	AD1743	5,59	-	3,03	B&W grund 6 timbers (Daly 1997a&c)
N_Oslo big	AD1308	AD1842	5,21	-	-	Oslo pines april 2016 110 timbers (Daly unpubl)
21014M02	AD1530	AD1759	4,98	4,17	3,03	Copenhagen B&W grund 10 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
2101XM01	AD1364	AD1863	3,47	5,36	-	Copenhagen B&W grund pine 35 timbers (Daly 1997a&c)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	3,43	4,36	-	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
Saltwick	AD1668	AD1755	\	4,05	-	Saltwick Shore Whitby N Yorkshire (Groves pers comm)
21011M04	AD1683	AD1819	\	4,42	-	Copenhagen B&W grund 2 trees (Daly 1996a&c)
21015M01	AD1530	AD1746	-	-	4,26	Copenhagen B&W grund 10 trees (Daly 1996a&c)
B027pine pipes	AD1581	AD1749	-	-	4,75	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine pipes 5 timbers (Daly this report)
2101M004	AD1540	AD1740	-	-	4,80	Copenhagen B&W grund 4 timbers (Daly 1997a&c)
00000072	AD1520	AD1858	-	3,55	4,09	North Germany (Bartholin pers comm)

Table 12. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4A land ties phase. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curves from the pines from the Phase 4A land ties phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Filenames	-	-	B027oak F green lt1	B027312a	B0273249	B0273259	
-	start	dates	AD1483	AD1642	AD1509	AD1573	
-	dates	end	AD1690	AD1730	AD1689	AD1679	
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	14,39	4,38	5,76	-	Copenhagen B&W grund 24 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	11,33	4,75	5,01	-	South Norway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl)
Z010m001	AD1480	AD1727	10,39	4,39	5,34	-	Larvik 5 & 6 Norway 8 timbers (Daly 2007b)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	9,75	3,80	4,45	-	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
B027oak E pink	AD1315	AD1663	8,57	\	5,17	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak pink 5 timbers (Daly this report)
Z049m001	AD1622	AD1716	8,52	5,63	5,68	3,05	Kampedal 3 Ulvøysund Aust Agder båd 2 timbers (Daly 2010a)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	8,29	\	-	-	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	7,45	\	-	\	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	7,05	4,10	3,12	-	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
Z065M003	AD1355	AD1617	6,70	\	-	-	Bjørвика Kenneth Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2011d)
Z094M001	AD1465	AD1650	6,52	\	-	-	Portørenga Norge 3 timbers (Daly 2013c)
Z138M001	AD1431	AD1610	6,39	\	-	-	Oslo Operaen Europark 2 timbers (Daly 2015b)
Z071m004	AD1304	AD1595	5,89	\	-	\	Barcode Oslo ship BC08 5 timbers (Daly 2011e)
B027pine C ...	AD1484	AD1642	5,48	\	-	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 5 timbers (Daly this report)
Z0307M01	AD1435	AD1585	5,28	\	-	\	Barcode ship BC07 5 timbers (Daly 2010b)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	5,14	-	3,33	-	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)
Z029m001	AD1583	AD1803	5,14	3,52	-	-	Orekilen 2 timbers (Daly 2008b)
Z027M001	AD1313	AD1567	5,01	\	-	\	Amager Strand 6 planks (Daly 2008a)
9M456781	109BC	AD1986	4,13	4,53	-	-	Jylland/Fyn

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							(Nationalmuseet)
DM100007	AD1080	AD1967	-	4,25	-	4,00	Hamburg (Hamburg Uni)
G340VZ01	AD1641	AD1722	-	-	3,96	4,98	Wolfenbüttel 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H115SM01	AD1542	AD1695	-	-	-	4,55	Moelln Hauptstr. 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 13. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4A land ties phase. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curves and three single curves from the oaks from the Phase 4A land ties phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

For the oaks from the Phase 4A land tie phase one main group can be suggested as shown in table 11. The average (B027oak F green It1) contains nine trees and is 208 years long. Two additional tree-ring curves correlate somewhat with this group, but have not been included in the average. One curve (B0273259) distinctly falls outside the oak group, and in fact this is from a tree felled slightly earlier than the rest of the oak, in winter AD 1679-80 (fig. 10). The large oak group and the two other single timbers are dating with Scandinavian oak tree-ring datasets (table 13) achieving highest correlation with Norwegian chronologies and with site chronologies of Norwegian imported timber. The last oak is dated but it is not possible to identify its provenance.

Phase 4 bulwarks

There are 56 timber samples assigned to the Phase 4 bulwark of which 44 were analysed dendrochronologically and 34 of these dated. Of the samples not analysed one contained too few rings, and the other 11 were stored for possible later analysis, but it was not judged necessary to add these to the extensive analysis for this phase. Of the 10 undated samples six are pine, one is spruce/larch and three are oak. They represent a bulwark running east-west across the excavation site including closely spaced upright posts and both horizontal and vertical planking. Several timbers, all upright posts, four of oak and two of pine, dated to c. 1690 (fig. 11) and their position (using numbers) is marked in the plan of the site that shows the 1690s & 1730s phases (fig. 9). The majority of the remaining samples that could be dated from the Phase 4 bulwark phase are dated to around the 1740s-50s (fig. 11 & fig. 14). By far the majority of these are of oak (just two of the 27 are pine). Fourteen of the oaks from this phase have sapwood preserved and three have bark edge. Two of them are from trees felled in winter AD 1753-54 while the third is from winter AD 1754-55. The estimated felling date for the remaining oaks would allow that these trees to be felled also around AD 1753-55, and are marked with turquoise in fig. 12. The dating of two pine samples; one from a tree felled after AD 1737, the other after AD 1756, probably also belong to the mid-1750s building phase. One last pine sample is dating to AD 1868 and clearly must belong to a different phase than Phase 4. It was situated at the west end of the site and is probably part of the crane structure discussed below.

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Fig. 11. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwarks. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

Two of the oaks from the earlier 1690 dating are grouped together (B027oak F green gr1), but the other two oaks do not form any group. The correlation values for Group 1 are shown in table 15 and a South Norway provenance is likely. The other two also appear to have a similar provenance.

The oaks from the 1750s phase form one main group but four samples fall outside this (table 14). The correlation results (table 16) suggest a Northern European provenance for these timbers, but the high correlations are so spread geographically, from Northern Poland to Lower Saxony, that a more precise determination of the source of these trees is not possible.

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Table 14. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwarks. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values. See full table in Appendix 5

Filenames	-	-	B027oak F green gr1	
-	start	dates	AD1413	
-	dates	end	AD1689	
SNorway ships	AD1304	AD1895	8,50	SNorway ships 63 timbers (Daly unpubl)
21015M02	AD1305	AD1743	7,86	B&W grund 24 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
Z096M001	AD1378	AD1517	7,17	Bispevika 2 ship Oslo 3 timbers (Daly 2013d)
FTMAS2	AD1318	AD1572	6,74	Fenton Tower Scotland IMPORTS 5 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z010m001	AD1480	AD1727	6,63	Larvik 5 & 6 Norway 8 timbers (Daly 2007b)
Z071m004	AD1304	AD1595	6,40	Barcode Oslo ship BC08 5 timbers (Daly 2011e)
StSerfM001	AD1377	AD1511	6,39	St Serfs church Dysart IMPORTS 7 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z059m001	AD1371	AD1659	6,25	Klim Strandvraget 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
Z062m001	AD1384	AD1512	6,14	Oslo Vaterland I Schweigaardsgt 5 timbers (Daly 2011b)
8127M001	AD846	AD1771	5,85	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000a 2001a)
B027oak E pink	AD1315	AD1663	5,59	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak pink 5 timbers (Daly this report)
EDINCAS2	AD1358	AD1509	5,47	Edinburgh Castle 13 timbers (Crone pers comm)
Z065M002	AD1355	AD1617	5,30	Bjørsvika Kenneth Oslo 4 timbers (Daly 2011d)
B027oak F green	AD1483	AD1690	4,81	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak F green lt1 9 timbers (Daly this report)
SM000005	AD1274	AD1974	4,50	Skåne Blekinge (Lund University)

Table 15. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwark. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the group 1 oaks from the Phase 4 bulwark and diverse master and site chronologies.

Filenames	-	-	B027337 &339&34 1 same tree	B027oak F green main	
-	start	dates	AD1570	AD1529	
-	dates	end	AD1740	AD1754	
B027oak F g	AD1508	AD1748	4,69	13,91	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak F green lt2 19 timbers (Daly this report)
B003M001	AD1563	AD1731	3,75	13,13	Vindebrogade Copenhagen imports (Daly 2003)
G3710Z01	AD1508	AD1694	-	9,60	Near Jork Hamburg 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
0697001M	AD1554	AD1986	-	9,59	PL Wolin (Wazny pers comm)
DM200006	AD914	AD1873	4,36	9,56	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)

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PM670108	AD725	AD1985	3,73	9,33	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	4,68	9,10	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
G350YZ01	AD1460	AD1742	3,49	8,82	Hitzacker Göttingen 9 timbers (Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G340VZ02	AD1482	AD1692	3,39	8,21	Wolfenbüttel 10 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
GO10TZ01	AD1493	AD1731	-	7,86	Güstrow 7 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z146M003	AD1517	AD1699	-	7,82	Raasepori Jussarö Finland 7 timbers (Daly 2015d)
G352YZ01	AD1509	AD1699	-	7,64	Dreilingen 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G361CZ01	AD1535	AD1708	3,49	7,56	Holto 5 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200003	AD1004	AD1970	3,91	7,49	Weserbergland (Göttingen Uni)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	3,81	7,48	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
21015M01	AD1530	AD1746	3,71	7,42	B&W grund 10 trees (Daly 1996)
G311MZ01	AD1382	AD1771	-	7,23	Hann.Münden 10 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
GO11QZ01	AD1543	AD1719	-	7,13	Stralsund 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G342JZ01	AD1592	AD1727	4,04	7,03	Osterweik 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM100007	AD1080	AD1967	-	7,00	Hamburg (Hamburg Uni)

Table 16. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwark. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curves from the oaks from the Phase 4 bulwark and diverse master and site chronologies.

The correlation values for the dated pine samples between each other are shown in table 16. No averages are made for these, as the correlations do not suggest any meaningful groupings. The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the five pines and master and site chronologies for pine for Northern Europe are shown in table 19. The two earlier c. 1690 pines are dating with quite separate tree-ring datasets; one with data from around the upper Baltic, one with data from Norway. The two mid-18th century pines date best with chronologies from other mid-18th century structures from the Gammel Strand excavation (described below) and the 19th century pine is dating against other 19th century material from this excavation.

Filenames	-	-	B027655 a	B027668 a	B027657 a	B027659 9	B027672 a	
-	start	dates	AD1579	AD1451	AD1590	AD1636	AD1711	
-	dates	end	AD1690	AD1673	AD1737	AD1751	AD1868	
B027pine crane	AD1701	AD1868	\	\	-	-	6,35	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine crane 3 timbers (Daly this report)
B027pine fi.	AD1700	AD1823	\	\	-	-	6,34	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine fiskegangen 4 timbers (Daly this report)

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B027pine bl.	AD1715	AD1823	\	\	\	-	5,73	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine blue gr1 3 timbers (Daly this report)
B027pine F	AD1592	AD1744	-	-	6,84	3,33	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine F green lt2 2 timbers (Daly this report)
B027pine pipes	AD1581	AD1749	3,91	-	5,11	6,77	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine pipes 5 timbers (Daly this report)
00000072	AD1520	AD1858	-	-	5,74	5,48	-	Northern Germany (Bartholin pers comm)
21014M02	AD1530	AD1759	-	-	5,57	4,37	-	Copenhagen B&W Grund 10 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
pol_kuja	AD1168	AD2000	-	-	5,08	3,39	-	Kuyavian-Pomerania Poland (Zielski & Kamiński 2003)
Danson55	AD1494	AD1705	-	6,52	-	-	\	Danson House Bexley Kent (Groves pers comm)
SWED_HRJ	AD1349	AD1788	-	6,30	-	-	-	Härjedalen (Bartholin pers comm)
99200010	AD871	AD1986	3,45	6,29	-	-	-	Norway south-east Oestlandet (Thun pers comm)
99500010	AD765	AD1996	-	6,27	-	-	-	Norway south-west Vestland (Thun pers comm)
Rangr-P1	AD1246	AD1632	-	6,08	-	\	\	Rangers House Greenwich Park London (Groves pers comm)
SWED_JM2	AD1305	AD1827	-	5,92	-	-	-	Jaemtland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_DAL	AD1001	AD1852	-	5,69	-	-	-	Dalarna (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED305	AD1450	AD2002	-	5,15	-	-	-	Bjorbo Dalarna (Torbjorn Axelson ITRDB)
medpin01	AD1345	AD1859	-	5,07	-	-	-	Medelpad (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	5,73	-	3,14	-	4,90	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_STK	AD1127	AD1671	5,54	-	3,11	-	\	Stockholm/Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
30160009	AD1573	AD1764	5,51	-	-	-	-	Naes Herrgaard (Bartholin pers comm)

Table 17. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwark. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the pine tree-ring curves from the Phase 4 bulwark and diverse master and site chronologies.

SG618 Live well

Seven samples were taken from a box construction found to the west end of the site (fig. 9). It is suggested that the box was for fish storage. All samples are of oak from tangentially cut planks. It was decided to analyse just five of these samples, as the results that emerged were so uniform so it was judged unnecessary to analyse them all.

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The analysis showed that four of the five have such high agreement that all four might have been fashioned out of a single tree. One of the samples had sapwood preserved. The tree samples came from was felled in AD 1731-45, and the box was probably made within these dates (fig. 11).

An average representing 2 trees was made (B027oak SG618 Live well) which is 174 years in length. The correlation of the average with tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe indicates a Northern German provenance but with so few trees represented in the average, a detailed provenance determination is not possible (table 19).

Fig. 11. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, SG618 Live well. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

		B027543a	B0275449	B027547a	B027546a	B027545a	
B027oak fishbox		B027543a	*	4,73	3,59	3,96	3,58
	Same tree	B0275449	4,73	*	21,9	15,89	14,26
		B027547a	3,59	21,9	*	12,26	11,66
		B027546a	3,96	15,89	12,26	*	12,31
		B027545a	3,58	14,26	11,66	12,31	*

Table 18. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, fish storage box. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

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Filenames	-	-	B027oak SG618 Live well	
-	start	dates	AD1558	
-	dates	end	AD1731	
GO10JZ01	AD1576	AD1728	5,80	Güstrow 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
H11HZM02	AD1584	AD1721	5,28	Lübeck Engelsgrube 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
2101M003	AD1540	AD1746	5,24	Copenhagen B&W Grund (Daly 1997a&c)
B003M001	AD1563	AD1731	5,12	Vindebrogade Copenhagen (Daly 2003)
G3908Z01	AD1604	AD1699	5,10	Quakenbrück 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z146M001	AD1560	AD1699	5,06	Raasepori Jussarö Finland ship 4 timbers (Daly 2015d)
G372FZ01	AD1549	AD1676	4,98	Oldenburg 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
HO13AM02	AD1561	AD1655	4,91	Wismar Luebschestr. 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	4,90	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
DM100008	AD457	AD1723	4,81	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
H115SM01	AD1542	AD1695	4,53	Moelln Hauptstr. 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
0697001M	AD1554	AD1986	4,39	PL Wolin (Wazny pers comm)

Table 19. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, SG618 Live well. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the oaks from the box and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Phase 4B land ties

There are 25 dendrochronological samples taken from this phase of land ties and all were analysed. Three of the samples are of pine, and the remainder are oak. Three oaks and one pine could not be dated. Just three of the dated oak samples have sapwood preserved. The estimated felling dates for the trees that these three samples come from are AD 1741-56, AD 1748-60 and AD 1749-60 respectively (fig. 12). If these three trees were felled at the same felling event, then we might combine the felling estimates and suggest that felling took place between c. 1749 and c. 1756 (marked with turquoise fig. 13). The rest of the dated oaks can have been felled within this timeframe. It is clear from this result that the Phase 4B land ties are contemporary with the Phase 4 bulwark discussed above, and both these are illustrated in fig. 13.

The two dated pines are from trees felled in 1734 or shortly after and after AD 1761 respectively. One of the pine land ties thus must have been put in place as a later repair.

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Fig. 12. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4B land ties phase. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this construction phase.

Fig. 13. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwark and Phase 4B land tie phase. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

The correlation between every tree-ring curve from the Phase 4B land ties phase with each other is shown in table 20. The two pines cross-match and an average (B027pine F green It2) of these two are 153 years long. The curve matches with tree-ring datasets for

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pine from Copenhagen, which are based on imports and from Northern Poland, but there is no clear indication of where these two trees might have grown.

The oaks from this phase also can be assembled into one group (table 20) and the average of these (B027oak F green lt2) is 241 years long. As can be seen from the correlations in table 22 this average matches very well with the main oak group from the Phase 4 bulwark discussed above and with site chronologies for Northern continental Europe.

Table 20. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4B land ties. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values. See full table in Appendix 6

Filenames	-	-	B027pine F green lt2	
-	start	dates	AD1592	
-	dates	end	AD1744	
DANPIN01	AD1380	AD1853	6,68	B&W-Grunden Copenhagen (Daly 1997a&c)
pol_kuja	AD1168	AD2000	4,98	Kuyavian-Pomerania Poland (Zielski & Kamiński 2003)
DANSON2	AD1545	AD1767	4,96	Danson House Bexley Kent IMPORTS (Groves pers comm)
pol_skan	AD1168	AD1994	4,91	Poland north central Pomorze Kujawy Mazury Mazowsze (Andrzej Zielski)
B027pine pipes	AD1581	AD1749	4,56	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine pipes 5 timbers (Daly this report)

Table 21. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4B land tie phase. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the pine average curve from the Phase 4B land tie phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

Filenames	-	-	B027oak F green lt2	
-	start	dates	AD1508	
-	dates	end	AD1748	
B027oak F g	AD1529	AD1754	13,91	Gammel Strand Copenhagen oak F green main 21 timbers (Daly this report)
B003M001	AD1563	AD1731	11,55	Copenhagen Vindebrogade 10 timbers (Daly 2003)
GO11QZ01	AD1543	AD1719	9,63	Stralsund 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
0697001M	AD1554	AD1986	9,37	PL Wolin (Wazny pers comm)

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DM200006	AD914	AD1873	8,37	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
G3703Z04	AD1587	AD1712	8,04	Buxtehude 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z146M003	AD1517	AD1699	8,02	Raasepori Jussarö Finland 7 timbers (Daly 2015d)
G3710Z01	AD1508	AD1694	7,73	Near Jork Hamburg 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G6B0DZ01	AD1524	AD1734	7,72	Bebra Bruecke 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G350YZ01	AD1460	AD1742	7,59	Hitzacker 9 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	7,44	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
G340VZ02	AD1482	AD1692	7,26	Wolfenbüttel 10 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G350RZ01	AD1523	AD1668	7,12	Celle 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3206Z03	AD1547	AD1725	7,02	Stadoldendorf 16 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G342JZ01	AD1592	AD1727	6,88	Osterweik 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
Z049m001	AD1622	AD1716	6,71	Kampedal 3 Ulvøysund Aust Agder båd 2 timbers (Daly 2010a)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	6,67	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
DM200003	AD1004	AD1970	6,50	Weserbergland (Göttingen Uni)
G361CZ01	AD1535	AD1708	6,49	Holto 5 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3506Z01	AD1585	AD1991	6,43	Göhrde 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
21015M01	AD1530	AD1746	6,38	Copenhagen B&W grund 10 trees (Daly 1996)
HO34MM01	AD1562	AD1735	6,33	Boitzenb. Klingbergs 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007a)
GO10JZ01	AD1576	AD1728	6,25	Güstrow 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)

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G352YZ01	AD1509	AD1699	6,20	Dreilingen 3 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G341AZ02	AD1525	AD1728	6,12	Wolfenbüttel 13 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G314TZ01	AD1594	AD1785	6,10	Helmarshausen 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)
G3128Z01	AD1488	AD1780	6,09	Hardeggen 9 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007a)

Table 22. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4B land tie phase. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the oak average curve from the Phase 4B land tie phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

Given the high agreement between the oaks from the Phase 4 bulwark and the Phase 4B land ties, both in terms of the correlations between the material from these two structures and in terms of the dating, this material has also been assessed dendrochronologically as a single group. Even when the material is grouped in smaller units, based on their correlation (not illustrated) still no clear provenance determination is emerging, in that the small groups also achieve a very wide geographical distribution of high correlation when compared with Northern European oak tree-ring datasets.

Phase 4 Building west SG410 of G537

A total of 12 samples from a building at the west end of the excavation (fig 14) were submitted for dendrochronological analysis. All samples are of pine, and all were analysed. Five samples are dated. Of the seven undated samples, five have fewer than 50 tree-rings.

The tree-ring curves from two of the dated samples are so similar (see table 23), the two samples could be taken from the same tree and these are therefore averaged to a single curve to represent that tree.

Three samples have bark edge preserved and these three are from two trees felled in the same year, in winter AD 1778-79 (marked with turquoise in fig. 15). Two remaining samples did not have bark edge, but these might have been felled at the same time. However, given that these two belong to a separate group (group 1), it is equally possible that these are from a different felling event (see fig. 15).

The correlation between the dated samples indicates that two distinct groups are present (table 27). Two average chronologies are therefore made as indicated; B027pine west end gr1 is 110 years long while B027pine west end gr2 is 79 years in length. The trees that form group 1 might have grown in the Southern Baltic region, while those forming group 2 might be from the Scandinavian Baltic region (table 24).

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Fig. 14. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, building west end. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

Fig. 15. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, foundations of building west end (SG410 of G537). Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

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			B0270019	B0270029	B0276449	B0276459	B0276469
B027pine westend gr1		B0270019	*	5,08	-	-	-
		B0270029	5,08	*	-	-	-
B027pine westend gr2	Same tree	B0276449	-	-	*	13,91	4,86
		B0276459	-	-	13,91	*	3,54
		B0276469	-	-	4,86	3,54	*

Table 23. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, building west end. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	B027pine westend gr1	B027pine westend gr2	
-	start	dates	AD1667	AD1700	
-	dates	end	AD1776	AD1778	
<i>Chronologies</i>					
pol_skan	AD1168	AD1994	6,16	3,53	Poland north central {Pomorze Kujawy Mazury Mazowsze} (Andrzej Zielski)
00000072	AD1520	AD1858	5,76	3,85	Nordtyskland (Bartholin pers comm)
pol_kuja	AD1168	AD2000	5,52	3,96	Kuyavian-Pomerania Poland (Zielski & Kamiński 2003)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	4,46	9,01	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
Swed_mal	AD1083	AD1992	3,22	7,40	Malardalen Gotland Sweden (Alf Bråthen)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	3,89	7,12	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED302	AD1582	AD1995	3,09	5,99	Naemdoe Stockholm archipelago (Lars Ake Larsson ITRDB)
SWED304	AD1667	AD1779	-	5,81	Sisshammar Tomas Andreason (ITRDB)
SWED_GTA	AD1636	AD1855	3,95	4,29	Götaland (Bartholin pers comm)
<i>Imports</i>					
WC-PISY	AD1641	AD1798	6,79	-	Windsor Castle Berkshire (Groves pers comm)
Hsemill	AD1608	AD1801	6,08	3,07	House Mill Bromley by Bow London (Groves pers comm)
21014M02	AD1530	AD1759	5,09	-	Copenhagen B&W grund 10 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
21011M04	AD1683	AD1819	-	5,83	Copenhagen B&W grund 2 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
2101XM01	AD1364	AD1863	-	5,33	Copenhagen B&W grund pine 35 timbers (Daly 1997a&c)
tmfasq05	AD1670	AD1806	3,56	4,36	Devon Warleigh House Tamerton Foliot (Groves pers comm)

Table 24. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, building west end. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curves from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Phase 5

Waterfront

Nine samples from a possible waterfront (fig. 16) were taken for dendrochronological analysis. Two had too few rings, so just seven were analysed, which were all of pine. Of these, four could be dated. None of the dated samples had bark edge preserved so the dates of the felling of the trees used for this structure are termini post quem, in the 18th century (marked with blue in fig. 17).

As indicated in table 25, three of the tree-ring curves from samples from this structural phase cross-match, and an average is made (B027pine waterfront) of 136 years in length. The correlation of this average (table 26) indicates a Southern Baltic origin for the pines. The tree that the fourth dated sample comes from might have a quite different origin in that it is dating with Norwegian datasets.

Fig. 17. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 5 waterfront. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

Fig. 18. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, waterfront. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

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		B027256a	B027603a	B027601a	B0276809
B027pine waterfront	B027256a	*	4,28	-	-
	B027603a	4,28	*	4,53	-
	B027601a	-	4,53	*	-
	B0276809	-	-	-	*

Table 25. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, waterfront. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	B027pine waterfront	B0276809	
-	start	dates	AD1624	AD1693	
-	dates	end	AD1759	AD1758	
<i>Chronologies</i>					
pol_kuja	AD1168	AD2000	7,69	-	Kuyavian-Pomerania Poland (Zielski & Kamiński 2003)
pol_skan	AD1168	AD1994	6,99	-	Poland north central {Pomorze Kujawy Mazury Mazowsze} (Andrzej Zielski)
00000072	AD1520	AD1858	6,40	-	Nordtyskland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_JM3	AD1384	AD1827	-	4,53	Sweden Jamtland (Bartholin pers comm)
LUDOMO_S	AD1667	AD1828	-	4,77	Luddomo in Selbu Norway Spruce 5 beams (Eidem 1953)
SWED023	AD1107	AD1827	-	5,08	Jamtland (Fritz Schweingruber)
GAULDL_P	AD1609	AD1940	-	5,08	Gauldalsforet Norway Pine 34 tree (Eidem 1953)
HOLT LN_P	AD1609	AD1940	-	5,21	Holtalen Norway Pine 10 trees (Eidem 1953)
TYDAL_P	AD1527	AD1936	-	5,43	Tydal Norway Pine 3 trees (Eidem 1953)
<i>Imports</i>					
Hsemill	AD1608	AD1801	6,43	-	House Mill Bromley by Bow London (Groves pers comm)
B027pine pipes	AD1581	AD1749	5,70	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine pipes 5 timbers (Daly this report)
21014M02	AD1530	AD1759	5,04	-	Copenhagen B&W 10 trees (Daly 1997a&c)

Table 26. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 5 waterfront. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the phase and one single tree-ring curve and diverse master and site chronologies.

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N-S plank structures, G578 and G593

A total of 10 samples from two N-S plank structures at the east end of the excavation (fig . 18) were submitted for dendrochronological analysis and all 10 were analysed. The samples are all of pine. Only four could be dated.

None of the dated samples had bark edge preserved. The outermost preserved tree-ring is on sample B0270129 and the tree that this sample comes from was felled after AD 1802 (fig. 19). The remaining three trees might have been felled at a similar period.

The correlation between the dated samples is shown in table 29. One chronology has been made, of four trees ('B027pine N-S structure F' is 346 years long).

The trees that form the group are dating with Finnish tree-ring datasets (table 30).

Fig. 18. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, N-S plank structures, G578 and G593. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarbø Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

Fig. 19. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, N-S plank structures G578 and G593. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

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		B0270129	B027611a	B027612a	B0276139
B027pine N-S structure	B0270129	*	3,34	3,85	3,32
	B027611a	3,34	*	2,96	2,68
	B027612a	3,85	2,96	*	3,25
	B0276139	3,32	2,68	3,25	*

Table 27. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, N-S plank structures. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	B027pine N-S structure	B027pine N-S structure	
-	start	dates	AD1457	AD1457	
-	dates	end	AD1802	AD1785	
FMP0004A	AD1375	AD1984	9,98	7,56	Finland North-Karelia (P.Zetterberg pers comm)
FIN.itrdb.001	AD1590	AD1984	9,94	6,17	Finland Ilomantsi Sivakkovaara (Matti Eronen ITRDB)
FIN.itrdb.005	AD1589	AD1984	7,27	4,61	Lieksa Koivujoki North Karelia (Matti Eronen ITRDB)
LAPPIN01	AD1483	AD1770	6,49	4,25	Huse Lapland (Bartholin pers comm)
finl068_pisy	AD1602	AD1841	6,11	4,91	Finland Nevala Juuka (Meriläinen, Lindholm, Timonen & Kolström ITRDB)
medpin01	AD1345	AD1859	5,84	4,67	Sweden Medelpad (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED023	AD1107	AD1827	5,73	3,17	Jamtland (F Schweingruber ITRDB)
FIN.itrdb.021	AD1659	AD1992	5,21	5,61	Uusijoki Finland (M. Lindholm J. Merilainen ITRDB)
SWED_HRJ	AD1349	AD1788	5,16	-	Härjedalen [Bartholin pers comm]

Table 28. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, N-S plank structures. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

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Fiskegangen G583, Phase 5.

Twelve samples from the so-called ‘fiskegang’ (fig. 20) were taken for dendrochronology, but eight of these were not prioritised for analysis. All four analysed samples from this structure, all pine, could be dated.

Three of the dated samples have bark edge preserved and are from trees felled in winter AD 1822-23, winter AD 1823-24 and in AD 1823-24 respectively. The fourth sample, from a tree felled after AD 1811 probably belongs to a similar felling phase (see fig. 21).

The correlation between the dated samples is shown in table 29. A chronology has been made, of all four trees (B027pine fiskegangen) which are 124 years in length.

The trees are dating chiefly with Swedish tree-ring datasets (table 30).

Fig. 20. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Fiskegangen G583 in blue. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

Fig. 21. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, fiskegangen G583 in Phase 5. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

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		B0272439	B0272629	B0272409	B0272519
B027pine fiskegangen	B0272439	*	3,61	3,83	4,32
	B0272629	3,61	*	9,7	3,57
	B0272409	3,83	9,7	*	6,17
	B0272519	4,32	3,57	6,17	*

Table 29. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Fiskegangen. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	B027pine fiskegangen	
-	start	dates	AD1700	
-	dates	end	AD1823	
B027pine bl...	AD1715	AD1823	8,53	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine blue gr1 3 timbers (Daly this report)
B027pine crane	AD1701	AD1868	8,02	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine crane 3 timbers (Daly this report)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	7,11	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	6,70	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
21021M11	AD1687	AD1854	6,33	Copenhagen Kongens Nytorv 3 trees (Daly 1998a)
SWED_AAL	AD1068	AD1827	6,13	Aaland (Bartholin pers comm)
litpinus-1	AD1487	AD2002	5,76	Lithuania pine (Vitas 2008)
SCAPIN01	AD1745	AD1990	5,63	Nytteboda (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GTA	AD1636	AD1855	5,18	Göteborg (Bartholin pers comm)
Swed_mal	AD1083	AD1992	5,16	Malardalen Gotland Sweden (Alf Brathen)
21011M04	AD1683	AD1819	5,00	Copenhagen B&W grund 2 trees (Daly 1996)

Table 30. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, fiskegangen G583. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

Phase 5 land tie group G562

There are 22 samples analysed from the Phase 5 group G562 (fig. 22), all pine. Nine of these are dated. One additional sample was possibly from this structural phase, so is included in this group. It is also dated.

The dating results suggest that the structure comprises several phases, or that there are timbers re-used in the main phase of construction. In one example, the assignment of the timber to the Phase 5 construction phase might be incorrect. In fig. 23 the chronological position of the dated samples is shown. One sample, from a tree felled possibly in AD 1726 (possible bark edge), might have been incorrectly assigned, and might originally have been part of the Phase 4 bulwark built in the 1730s. Two other

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samples with felling dated estimated at after 1747 and possibly 1790, respectively might be re-used in this structure. The main felling activity for Phase 5 probably was in AD 1822-23 (marked with blue in fig. 26), represented by five samples (group 1), indicating that this phase probably coincides with the *fiskegang* described above. Additional Phase 5 land ties were added after AD 1835 (group 2) (see fig. 23).

The correlation between the dated samples is shown in table 31. Two chronologies have been made; group 1 (Average pine gr1) is made from four samples, representing 3 trees, and is 109 years long, group 2 (Average pine gr2) is of just two trees and is 115 years in length).

The two groups are dating chiefly with other tree-ring datasets for pine imported to Copenhagen (table 32). The singly dated samples are dating with a widely differing range of tree-ring datasets as seen in table 33.

Fig. 22. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 5 land tie group G562 (in blue). Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

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Fig. 23. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 5 land tie G562 (blue line). Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

		B0276249	B0272469	B0272719	B0272209	B0272509	B0276709	B027673a	B0272529	B0276639	B0276649
	B0276249	*	-	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
	B0272469	-	*	-	\	\	-	\	\	\	\
	B0272719	\	-	*	3,41	-	-	3,6	-	-	-
Average pine gr1	B0272209	\	\	3,41	*	5,93	5,9	3,82	-	-	-
	Same tree B0272509	\	\	-	5,93	*	16,26	5,59	-	-	-
	B0276709	\	-	-	5,9	16,26	*	6,28	-	-	-
	B027673a	\	\	3,6	3,82	5,59	6,28	*	3,19	-	-
	B0272529	\	\	-	-	-	-	3,19	*	-	-
Ave pine gr2	B0276639	\	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	7,42
	B0276649	\	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	7,42	*

Table 31. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 5 land ties G562. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	B027pine blue gr1	B027pine blue gr2	
-	start	dates	AD1715	AD1720	
-	dates	end	AD1823	AD1834	
B027pine fi...	AD1700	AD1823	8,53	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine fiskegangen 4 timbers (Daly this report)
B027pine crane	AD1701	AD1868	5,35	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine crane 3 timbers (Daly this report)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	5,37	-	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
21021M11	AD1687	AD1854	4,47	-	Copenhagen Kongens Nytorv 3 trees (Daly 1998a)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	4,26	4,40	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
Swed_mal	AD1083	AD1992	3,72	4,33	Malardalen Gotland Sweden (Alf Brathen)

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21011M01	AD1721	AD1853	-	9,31	Copenhagen B&W grund 8 trees pælrække (Daly 1997a&c)
2101XM01	AD1364	AD1863	-	9,03	Copenhagen B&W grund pine 35 timbers (Daly 1997a&c)

Table 32. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 5 land ties G562 (blue group 1 and 2). Table showing the correlation (t-test) between two average curves from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

Filenames	-	-	B027 2469	B027 2529	B027 2719	B027 6249	
-	start	dates	AD1662	AD1724	AD1706	AD1636	
-	dates	end	AD1746	AD1822	AD1790	AD1726	
B027pine fi	AD1700	AD1823	-	5.52	-	\	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine fiskegangen 4 timbers (Daly this report)
21021M11	AD1687	AD1854	-	4.87	-	3.84	Copenhagen Kongens Nytorv 3 trees (Daly 1998a)
scapin01	AD1745	AD1990	\	4.08	-	\	Nytteboda (Bartholin pers comm)
litpinus-1	AD1487	AD2002	-	-	4.38	-	Lithuania pine. (Vitas 2008)
SWED_GO T	AD1124	AD1987	-	-	4.03	9.86	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GR V	AD1469	AD1840	-	-	4.97	7.25	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GTA	AD1636	AD1855	-	-	-	4.69	Götaland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_AAL	AD1068	AD1827	-	-	3.75	4.05	Aaland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED302	AD1582	AD1995	-	-	4.64	4.51	Naemdoe Stockholm archipelago (Lars Ake Larsson)
SWED_JM2	AD1305	AD1827	4.03	-	-	-	Jaemtland (Bartholin pers comm)
SELYD_P	AD1424	AD1938	4.60	-	-	-	Selbu & Tydal Norway Pine 13 tree (Eidem 1953)
RORSTAD1	AD1396	AD1936	4.91	-	-	-	Rorstaddalen 1 Pine 20 trees (Ording 1941)
NOMK140 3	AD801	AD1979	4.04	-	-	-	Troendelag (Bartholin pers comm)
Danson1	AD1489	AD1758	-	-	4.34	-	Danson House

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							Bexley Kent (Groves pers comm)
tmfasq05	AD1670	AD1806	-	-	5.27	-	Devon Warleigh House Tamerton (Groves pers comm)
B027pine pipes	AD1581	AD1749	-	\	4.02	3.49	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine pipes 5 timbers (Daly this report)

Table 33. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, land tie G562 single trees. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between four independently dated samples from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

Concrete foundation group G589

Six samples from a concrete foundation (fig. 24) were taken for dendrochronology, all pine, and all were analysed. Three of the six samples analysed could be dated. All three of the dated samples have bark edge preserved. Two are from trees felled in winter 1868-69 and the third is from 1868-69, though the season cannot be determined (see fig 25).

Fig. 24. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, concrete foundation group G589. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

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Fig. 25. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, concrete foundation G589 Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

		B027201a	B027203a	B027202a
groB027pine concrete foundation	B027201a	*	5,22	3,4
	B027203a	5,22	*	9,11
	B027202a	3,4	9,11	*

Table 34. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, crane. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Filenames	-	-	B027pine concrete foundation	
-	start	dates	AD1701	
-	dates	end	AD1868	
B027pine fi.	AD1700	AD1823	8,02	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine fiskegangen 4 timbers (Daly this report)
21021M11	AD1687	AD1854	7,12	Copenhagen Kongens Nytorv 3 trees (Daly 1998a)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	5,52	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
B027pine bl.	AD1715	AD1823	5,35	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine blue gr1 3 timbers (Daly this report)
SWED302	AD1582	AD1995	5,10	Naemdoe Stockholm archipelago (Lars Ake Larsson)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	4,94	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
SCAPIN01	AD1745	AD1990	4,57	Nytteboda (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GTA	AD1636	AD1855	4,48	Götaland (Bartholin pers comm)

Table 35. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, concrete foundation G589. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

The correlation between the dated samples is shown in table 34. A chronology has been made, of all three trees (B027pine concrete foundation G583) which is 168 years long.

The trees are dating chiefly with Swedish tree-ring datasets (table 35).

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Pipes and drains

Several timber pipes and drains were found across the excavation site (fig. 15). Fifteen of these were samples for dendrochronological analysis and all but one was analysed. The 14 analysed samples are all of pine, but only half could be dated. (The undated ones are generally those with fewer than c. 90 rings, with just one exception.)

Some of the pipes had bark or bark edge preserved. Trees for these pipes had been felled in spring/summer AD 1686, winter 1725-26 and winter AD 1738-39 respectively (fig. 16). The remaining pipes that are dated did not have bark edge confirmed, and the dating for these are termini post quem in the 18th century.

Fig. 26. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, pipes and drains. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

Fig. 27. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, pipes and drains. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

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		B027265x	B027008a	B027225a	B027231a	B0276079	B027014a	B027270a
B027pine pipes	B027265x	*	4,53	-	-	-	-	-
	B027008a	4,53	*	4,03	4,13	4,08	-	-
	B027225a	-	4,03	*	6,10	3,07	-	-
	B027231a	-	4,13	6,10	*	-	-	-
	B0276079	-	4,08	3,07	-	*	-	-
	B027014a	-	-	-	-	-	*	-
	B027270a	-	-	-	-	-	-	*

Table 36. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, waterpipes. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values

Filenames	-	-	B027pine pipes	B027014a	B027270a	
-	start	dates	AD1581	AD1655	AD1624	
-	dates	end	AD1749	AD1774	AD1724	
<i>Chronologies</i>						
pol_kuja	AD1168	AD2000	7,51	5,21	-	Kuyavian-Pomerania Poland (Zielski & Kamiński 2003)
pol_skan	AD1168	AD1994	6,96	4,72	-	Poland north central {Pomorze Kujawy Mazury Mazowsze} (Andrzej Zielski)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	6,91	-	-	Gotland Pinus (Bartholin pers comm)
00000072	AD1520	AD1858	6,54	4,87	-	Nordtyskland (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED022	AD1127	AD1987	5,80	-	-	Gotland (Fritz Schweingruber)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	5,43	-	-	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
FIN.pisy.01	AD1623	AD1851	5,12	2,35	-	Savonlinna Finland (ITRDB)
finl023_pis...	AD1623	AD1851	4,90	2,24	-	East Finland (Meriläinen Lindholm Timonen ITRDB)
SWED023	AD1107	AD1827	-	-	3,12	Jamtland (Fritz Schweingruber)
NOR_VISD	AD1600	AD1983	-	-	3,41	Visdalen Norway (Briffa et al 1986)
SWED_HRJ	AD1349	AD1788	-	-	4,51	Härjedalen (Bartholin pers comm)
<i>Imports</i>						
21014M02	AD1530	AD1759	7,31	4,67	-	Copenhagen B&W 10 trees (Daly 1997a&c)
DANSON2	AD1545	AD1767	7,25	2,04	-	Danson House Bexley

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						Kent (Groves pers comm)
Hsemill	AD1608	AD1801	6,19	7,42	-	Mill Bromley by Bow London (Groves pers comm)
B027pine wa...	AD1624	AD1759	5,70	3,14	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine waterfront 3 timbers (Daly this report)
WCL-M35	AD1651	AD1751	5,00	2,34	-	Wallace Collection London (Groves pers comm)
B027pine F ...	AD1657	AD1727	-	4,58	-	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine F green lt1 gr2 2 timbers (Daly this report)

Table 37. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, waterpipes. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between the average curve from the phase and two single tree-ring curves and diverse master and site chronologies.

The correlations between the tree-ring curves from the timbers in this group are shown in table 36. A small group is identified, as shown, and an average of these is made (B027pine pipes) of 169 years in length. The material is dating with pine tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe (table 37), but pines in this period were so extensively traded, it is difficult to ascertain the origin of the pines used for the pipes.

Phase 6 samples

A total of 26 samples were taken from Phase 6 (location marked in fig. 28) and of these 23 were analysed. There was a single oak sample (not dated) while the rest are pine. Only three of the analysed samples could be dated (fig. 29). The tree-ring curves from the three do not achieve significant internal correlation, but are dated independently. As is suggested by the correlations achieved between the three dated tree-ring curves and tree-ring datasets for pine (table 38), these are probably Scandinavian timber, but re-used in the 19th century construction.

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Fig. 28. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 6. Plan of the site, after Camilla Haarby Hansen, showing the position of the construction.

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FileNames	-	-	B027205a	B027242a	B0276299	
-	start	dates	AD1640	AD1367	AD1678	
-	dates	end	AD1747	AD1715	AD1781	
<i>Chronologies</i>						
SWED_HRJ	AD1349	AD1788	5,42	6,80	-	Härjedalen (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_JM2	AD1305	AD1827	4,50	5,56	-	Jaemtland (Bartholin pers comm)
dalpinus	AD931	AD1888	4,17	6,58	-	Dalarna (Eggertsson pers comm)
helpin01	AD1001	AD1861	3,79	4,75	-	Helsingland (Bartholin pers comm)
JAMPIN02	AD1337	AD1865	-	7,19	-	Jaemtland Gunnarsson (Bartholin pers comm)
99500010	AD765	AD1996	-	5,69	-	Norway south-west (Thun pers comm)
N029M001	AD1308	AD1545	\	5,58	\	Bispevika 2 laftekasse 26 timbers (Daly forthcoming)
SWED_GRV	AD1469	AD1840	-	-	4,84	Gravsten (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED_GOT	AD1124	AD1987	-	-	4,74	Gotland (Bartholin pers comm)
<i>Imports</i>						
Rangr-P1	AD1246	AD1632	\	6,08	\	Rangers House Greenwich Park London (Groves pers comm)
Danson55	AD1494	AD1705	-	5,89	\	Danson House Bexley Kent (Groves pers comm)
JemGrp04	AD1507	AD1700	-	5,80	\	London-Westminster 107 Jermyn Street (Groves pers comm)
IMPORTx8	AD1329	AD1671	-	5,00	\	Scotland Imports 59 timbers (Crone pers comm)
B027oak C o	AD1331	AD1557	\	4,96	\	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 23 timbers (Daly this report)
B027pine we	AD1700	AD1778	-	\	5,26	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine westend gr2 2 timbers (Daly this report)

Table 38. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 6 single trees. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between three independently dated samples from the phase and diverse master and site chronologies.

Fig. 29. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 6. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated samples from this phase.

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Revisions

The dating of a very small number of samples reported previously (Daly 2013e) is revised here for this final report on the dendrochronological analysis for the Gammel Strand excavations. One sample is an oak (B0271069 KBM3828 Gammel Strand 202639 13814 QUSP) from the Phase 4 bulwarks that was erroneously dated previously. The revised dating reported here is the correct position for this sample. The dating of one pine sample (B0270129 KBM3828 Gammel Strand 13646 202628 PISY) is also revised. Finally, one sample (B0270069 KBM3828 Gammel Strand 17926 18441 PISY) that initially seemed to date is now not dated.

Discussion

The dendrochronological analysis of the extensive structures found at Gammel Strand during the excavations has not only provided us with a precise chronology for the many building phases on the site. The study has provided us with a detailed insight into the extent of traded timber through several centuries for the major investments in urban infrastructure that the quayside improvements represent. In terms of the timber types used there is a clear transition with time, from an exclusive use of oak in the 16th century which gradually is replaced with use of conifers, chiefly pine, in the following centuries (fig. 30). The diagram summarises the genus of the dated samples through time, but of the undated material the use of spruce is also very limited.

Fig. 30. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, distribution of wood genus, of the dated samples, through time.

Provenance

When a successful dating of the timber is reached it is also possible to identify the region of origin of the material, as indicated in the presentation of the results from each construction phase from the site described above. In fig. 31 it is attempted to summarise

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these results to see if a pattern, through time, of the timber procurement for harbour maintenance in the city over four centuries can be observed. The procurement of the oaks in the 16th century constructions is dominated by western Swedish timber while Norwegian oak and pine appear in the 17th. In the 18th century a large amount of the timber, dominated by oaks, is perhaps from the southern Baltic region (Germany and Poland/Germany in the diagram). The dated material from the 19th century, all pine, is dating with Scandinavian references, but there is a large proportion of undated samples from structures from this century, so a generalised statement on the procurement of timber for the 19th century on the basis of the results here would be risky.

Fig. 31. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, the source of the timber (provenance) of the dated samples, through time.

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Appendix 1 - table 1

			B027530a	B027502A	B0275299	B027533a	B027531a	B027535a	B027528a	B027501A	B027505A	B027508a	B0271099	B027510a	B027513a	B027507a	B027534a	B027504A	B027512a	B027509a	B027532a	B027503A	B027558a	B027511a	B027506A	
Average oak B027oak B Phase 1		B027530a	*	4,93	3,02	3,72	4,92	3,69	4,14	4,98	3,99	4,00	5,13	3,21	3,8	-	3,1	4,68	5,32	5,82	-	3,79	4,57	4,55	\	
		B027502A	4,93	*	3,8	4,39	3,93	3,75	6,5	5,75	6,9	7,17	6,25	6,82	6,31	5,4	5	5,57	5,5	5,92	4	5,78	5,97	4,23	-	
		B0275299	3,02	3,8	*	-	5,97	7,27	6,84	3,95	6,83	5,3	4,45	3,73	3,69	4,99	4,33	3,25	4,18	5,37	5,53	3,74	3,72	3,7	-	
		B027533a	3,72	4,39	-	*	4,58	3,45	4,58	4,41	5,36	5,57	4,78	7,32	5,95	-	3,95	6,69	4,92	4,49	-	4,5	-	4,49	\	
		B027531a	4,92	3,93	5,97	4,58	*	7,38	3,77	6,31	5,19	5,94	5,15	6,54	4,9	4,36	4,97	4,26	4,85	4,93	-	-	-	5,21	\	
		B027535a	3,69	3,75	7,27	3,45	7,38	*	6,81	5,31	7,68	6,43	5,52	7,66	5,53	5,65	4,6	3,96	5,06	6,1	4,3	3,23	-	3,86	\	
		B027528a	4,14	6,5	6,84	4,58	3,77	6,81	*	6,36	8,9	7,92	5,22	7,44	4,85	6,77	3,11	4,92	4,48	6,67	6,33	3,6	4,99	4,72	4,18	
		B027501A	4,98	5,75	3,95	4,41	6,31	5,31	6,36	*	9,18	6,74	5,16	7,82	5,37	3,56	4,13	5,29	6,58	5,09	3,62	3,06	3,73	4,93	\	
		Same tree	B027505A	3,99	6,9	6,83	5,36	5,19	7,68	8,9	9,18	*	14,29	6,6	7,09	7,32	5,64	-	6,47	6,2	5,82	6,05	4,55	3,81	4,41	4,4
			B027508a	4,00	7,17	5,3	5,57	5,94	6,43	7,92	6,74	14,29	*	6,42	7,66	5,57	5,19	-	4,39	5,23	6,44	3,95	5,3	4,54	4,55	4,03
			B0271099	5,13	6,25	4,45	4,78	5,15	5,52	5,22	5,16	6,6	6,42	*	8,57	6,54	5,62	4,43	5,09	4,88	4,02	3,38	4,35	4,26	5,22	\
			B027510a	3,21	6,82	3,73	7,32	6,54	7,66	7,44	7,82	7,09	7,66	8,57	*	6,29	5,62	5,91	4,95	5,48	5,18	5,73	5,79	4,01	4,71	\
	B027513a		3,8	6,31	3,69	5,95	4,9	5,53	4,85	5,37	7,32	5,57	6,54	6,29	*	3,41	4,72	4,39	4,65	5,94	5,44	6,28	-	4,58	-	
	B027507a		-	5,4	4,99	-	4,36	5,65	6,77	3,56	5,64	5,19	5,62	5,62	3,41	*	5,08	-	4,07	6,23	4,61	4,8	-	3,51	-	
	B027534a		3,1	5	4,33	3,95	4,97	4,6	3,11	4,13	-	-	4,43	5,91	4,72	5,08	*	4,6	6,87	5,5	4,28	5,02	3,2	-	\	
	B027504A		4,68	5,57	3,25	6,69	4,26	3,96	4,92	5,29	6,47	4,39	5,09	4,95	4,39	-	4,6	*	7,62	3,26	3,44	3,21	3,77	5,09	\	
	B027512a		5,32	5,5	4,18	4,92	4,85	5,06	4,48	6,58	6,2	5,23	4,88	5,48	4,65	4,07	6,87	7,62	*	5,68	4,52	5,09	4,49	3,39	\	
	B027509a		5,82	5,92	5,37	4,49	4,93	6,1	6,67	5,09	5,82	6,44	4,02	5,18	5,94	6,23	5,5	3,26	5,68	*	5,59	5,47	3,93	4,41	-	
	B027532a		-	4	5,53	-	-	4,3	6,33	3,62	6,05	3,95	3,38	5,73	5,44	4,61	4,28	3,44	4,52	5,59	*	6,56	-	\	-	
	B027503A		3,79	5,78	3,74	4,5	-	3,23	3,6	3,06	4,55	5,3	4,35	5,79	6,28	4,8	5,02	3,21	5,09	5,47	6,56	*	-	\	3,13	
B027558a	4,57	5,97	3,72	-	-	-	4,99	3,73	3,81	4,54	4,26	4,01	-	-	3,2	3,77	4,49	3,93	-	-	*	4,87	-			
B027511a	4,55	4,23	3,7	4,49	5,21	3,86	4,72	4,93	4,41	4,55	5,22	4,71	4,58	3,51	-	5,09	3,39	4,41	\	\	4,87	*	\			
B027506A	\	-	-	\	\	\	4,18	\	4,4	4,03	\	\	-	-	\	\	\	\	-	-	3,13	-	\	*		

Appendix 2 - table 3

		B0275219	B027552a	B0275189	B0275649	B0275509	B027523a	B0275169	B027559a	B027520a	B0275539	B027514a	B027551a	B027565a	B027517a	B027515a	B027566a	B027519a	B027567a	B027522a	B027561a	B027562a	B027524a	B0275489	B0275499	B027563a	B0275609	B027633a	B0276409	B0276429	B0276419	B0276699	B027634a					
	B0275219	*	3,57	-	3,78	3,74	3,72	-	-	-	3,90	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
	B027552a	3,57	*	3,4	3,64	-	4,06	4,01	-	-	3,16	-	4,05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
B027oak C orange	B0275189	-	3,4	*	4,61	5,85	3,86	3,93	3,41	4,54	-	4,06	5,83	4,66	7,04	4,81	5,47	3,84	5,05	-	4,64	3,63	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	B0275649	3,78	3,64	4,61	*	6,01	5,28	4,19	4,45	4,36	6,26	4,85	5,13	5,25	5,49	6,73	6,57	4,35	5,28	4,84	-	-	3,09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	B0275509	3,74	-	5,85	6,01	*	-	3,28	4,21	3,98	3,47	4,32	3,59	4,52	4,46	4,1	5,5	4,14	4,96	-	4,01	-	4,02	-	3,69	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027523a	3,72	4,06	3,86	5,28	-	*	4,62	-	-	4,71	4,93	4,92	6,47	4,3	4,56	4,33	3	-	3,83	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B0275169	-	4,01	3,93	4,19	3,28	4,62	*	3,64	3,83	-	4,49	6,48	5,71	5,94	4,88	5,84	3,76	4,11	3,44	3,2	3,17	-	-	-	-	3,34	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027559a	-	-	3,41	4,45	4,21	-	3,64	*	-	4,29	3,91	5,06	5,67	3,85	5,34	5,89	5,12	6,53	3,8	3,44	4,28	4,97	-	4,23	3,51	3,66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027520a	-	-	4,54	4,36	3,98	-	3,83	-	*	-	3,14	6,6	6,12	5,49	4,74	5,11	3,53	5,29	-	4,59	-	-	-	3,81	-	3,16	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,08	-	-		
	B0275539	3,90	3,16	-	6,26	3,47	4,71	-	4,29	-	*	-	3,59	5,11	5,8	5,87	4,45	7,39	3,64	4,52	3,86	3,25	-	3,51	-	3,88	3,25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027514a	-	-	4,06	4,85	4,32	4,93	4,49	3,91	3,14	3,59	*	5,62	8,43	7,42	3,56	6,49	8,32	6,11	5,14	5,23	3,72	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027551a	-	4,05	5,83	5,13	3,59	4,92	6,48	5,06	6,6	5,11	5,62	*	8,71	8,05	6,24	8,55	4,72	5,97	4,65	3,36	3,46	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027565a	-	-	4,66	5,25	4,52	6,47	5,71	5,67	6,12	5,8	8,43	8,71	*	6,88	6,85	8,45	4,57	6,99	3,49	6,57	4,93	3,09	-	4,04	3,15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,1	-		
	B027517a	-	3,8	7,04	5,49	4,46	4,3	5,94	3,85	5,49	5,87	7,42	8,05	6,88	*	5,69	9,54	8,52	6,84	7,12	7,5	4,44	3,3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027515a	-	-	4,81	6,73	4,1	4,56	4,88	5,34	4,74	4,45	3,56	6,24	6,85	5,69	*	10,73	4,63	6,11	3,44	4,09	-	3,67	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027566a	-	-	5,47	6,57	5,5	4,33	5,84	5,89	5,11	7,39	6,49	8,55	8,45	9,54	10,73	*	7,64	8,26	4,97	7,25	6,36	4,94	3,57	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027519a	-	-	3,84	4,35	4,14	3	3,76	5,12	3,53	3,64	8,32	4,72	4,57	8,52	4,63	7,64	*	8,86	8,7	6,93	4,04	7,29	-	4,14	3,02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027567a	-	-	5,05	5,28	4,96	-	4,11	6,53	5,29	4,52	6,11	5,97	6,99	6,84	6,11	8,26	8,86	*	5,66	6,7	5,67	6,82	3,45	4,54	3,15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,09	-	
	B027522a	-	-	-	4,84	-	3,83	3,44	3,8	-	3,86	5,14	4,65	3,49	7,12	3,44	4,97	8,7	5,66	*	4,19	-	4,89	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027561a	-	-	4,64	-	4,01	-	3,2	3,44	4,59	3,25	5,23	3,36	6,57	7,5	4,09	7,25	6,93	6,7	4,19	*	7,45	4,85	4,47	5,81	6,07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,86	-	
	B027562a	-	-	3,63	-	-	-	3,17	4,28	-	-	3,72	3,46	4,93	4,44	-	6,36	4,04	5,67	-	7,45	*	4,55	3,64	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,01	4,19
	B027524a	-	-	-	3,09	4,02	-	-	4,97	-	-	-	-	3,09	3,3	3,67	4,94	7,29	6,82	4,89	4,85	4,55	*	3,77	3,79	3,47	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
B0275489	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,51	-	-	-	-	-	3,57	-	3,45	-	4,47	3,64	3,77	*	8,08	3,25	3,13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,48	
B0275499	-	-	-	-	3,69	-	-	-	4,23	3,81	-	-	-	4,04	-	-	4,14	4,54	-	5,81	-	3,79	8,08	*	7,55	4,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
B027563a	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,34	3,51	-	3,88	-	-	3,15	3,11	-	4	3,02	3,15	-	6,07	-	3,47	3,25	7,55	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B0275609	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,66	3,16	3,25	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,13	4,1	-	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
B027pine C orange	B027633a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	5,21	6,34	5,04	7,38	-	-				
	B0276409	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,21	*	13,16	7,16	9,17	-	-				
	B0276429	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6,34	13,16	*	8,41	9,14	-	-				
	B0276419	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,04	7,16	8,41	*	11,23	-	-				
	B0276699	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,08	-	-	-	3,1	-	-	-	-	3,09	-	3,86	4,19	-	3,48	-	-	-	7,38	9,17	9,14	11,23	*	-	-	-			
	B027634a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*			

Table 3. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, orange phase. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

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Appendix 3 - table 8

			B027540a	B027536a	B027554a	B027541a	B027539a	B0276049	B027619a	B027626a	B0276059	B027618a	B027622a	B027620a	B0276239	B0276279	B0276289	B0276679	B0276259	B0276069	B0276719	B0274059	B0274079	B0274069	B0274099	B0274089	B027410a	B027412a	B0274139	B027414a	
B027oak E pink		B02754	*	5	5,28	-	3,52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02753	5	*	7,67	6,12	4,61	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02755	5,28	7,67	*	4,59	4,54	-	-	-	-	3,87	-	-	-	-	3,1	-	-	3,23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02754	-	6,12	4,59	*	3,19	-	-	-	-	-	4,03	-	-	-	4,55	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02753	3,52	4,61	4,54	3,19	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,32	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Same tree	B02760	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	17,54	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,21	3,5	4,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B02761	-	-	-	-	-	-	17,54	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,54	-	3,56	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
B027pine E pink		B02762	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	3,74	3,53	3,24	4,21	5,63	6,28	-	-	-	-	-	3,11	-	-	-	-	-	3,85	3,66	-	
		B02760	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,74	*	7,65	6,41	5,31	7,39	-	3,58	3,88	3,46	3,52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02761	-	-	3,87	4,03	-	-	-	-	3,53	7,65	*	3,98	5,41	6,63	-	5,63	3,59	3,23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B02762	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,24	6,41	3,98	*	5,92	8,46	4,4	-	4,37	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,21	-	-	-	-	
	Same tree	B02762	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,21	5,31	5,41	5,92	*	11,98	6,34	3,25	3,62	-	-	-	-	3,07	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02762	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,63	7,39	6,63	8,46	11,98	*	5,69	-	5,39	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B02762	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,21	3,54	6,28	-	4,4	6,34	5,69	*	4,03	-	-	3,58	-	4,28	4,12	-	-	-	4,47	3,6	
B02766	-	-	3,1	4,55	-	-	-	-	3,5	-	-	3,58	5,63	-	3,25	-	-	*	-	-	4,1	-	-	3,73	-	-	-	4,55	3,33		
B02766	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,01	3,56	-	3,88	3,59	4,37	3,62	5,39	4,03	-	*	3,74	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
orange gotland	B02762	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,46	3,23	-	-	-	-	-	3,74	*	-	4,66	-	3,18	3,94	3,7	-	-	-	-		
	B02760	-	-	3,23	-	3,32	-	-	-	-	3,52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	3,09	-	-	3,12	-	-	-	-		
	B02767	-	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	*	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\		
B027spruce D red		B02740	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,11	-	-	-	-	3	3,58	4,1	-	4,66	-	*	16,2	8,55	9,12	7,45	4,6	5,32	6,75	6,11		
		B02740	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,09	\	16,2	*	7,44	7,48	7,91	4,41	5,32	6,24	6,74	
		B02740	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,28	-	-	3,18	-	8,55	7,44	*	14,51	4,51	-	3,65	5,52	5,52	
		B02740	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,55	-	-	-	-	3,07	-	4,12	3,73	-	-	3,94	-	9,12	7,48	14,51	*	5,27	-	5,41	6,25	5,34	
		B02740	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,7	3,12	7,45	7,91	4,51	5,27	*	8,64	3,85	4,22	5,49	
		B02741	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,6	4,41	-	-	8,64	*	-	-	3,31	
		B02741	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,85	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,32	5,32	3,65	5,41	3,85	-	*	7,47	3,89	
		B02741	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,66	-	-	-	-	-	4,47	4,55	-	-	6,75	6,24	5,52	6,25	4,22	-	7,47	*	5,92	
B02741	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,6	3,33	-	-	6,11	6,74	5,52	5,34	5,49	3,31	3,89	5,92	*			

Table 8. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, G674 and G648 bulwarks. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine, blue = spruce/larch. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Appendix 4 - table 11

		B0272379	B0272499	B0276769	B027216a	B027004a	B0272579	B0272599	B0272589	B0272489	B027678a	B027238a	B0272329	B027217a	B027637a	B0276369	B027016a	B027318b	B0273219	B027322a	B027104a	B027525a	B0273279	B027108a	B027526a	B027323a	B0273249	B027312a	B0273259
B027pine F green lt1 gr1	B0272379	*	-	4,53	-	-	3,36	-	-	3,33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B0272499	-	*	6,3	4,38	4,45	4,42	6,21	5,85	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B0276769	4,53	6,3	*	5,73	5,01	3,22	4,98	4,23	5,15	4,79	3,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027216a	-	4,38	5,73	*	4,2	4,12	6,52	3,84	5,41	3,52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027004a	-	4,45	5,01	4,2	*	7	5,85	4,52	4,27	3,18	4,37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B0272579	3,36	4,42	3,22	4,12	7	*	6,96	6,22	3,66	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,57	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B0272599	-	6,21	4,98	6,52	5,85	6,96	*	5,14	4,7	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B0272589	-	5,85	4,23	3,84	4,52	6,22	5,14	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,41	-	-	-	-
	B0272489	3,33	-	5,15	5,41	4,27	3,66	4,7	-	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B027678a	-	-	4,79	3,52	3,18	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027238a	-	-	3,5	-	4,37	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	3,81	-	-	-	-	4,47	-	3,51	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,93	-
Same tree	B0272329	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	18,4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027217a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,81	18,4	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ave gr2	B027637a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	4,76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B0276369	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,76	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027016a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,3	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B027oak F green lt1	B027318b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	3,44	-	3,19	-	-	3,18	-	-	-	-	
	B0273219	-	-	-	-	-	3,57	-	-	-	-	4,47	-	-	-	-	-	3,44	*	8,71	8,17	7,38	5,71	3,53	3,07	-	-	-	
	B027322a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8,71	*	11,11	6,41	3,92	3,95	-	-	3,94	-	
	B027104a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,51	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,19	8,17	11,11	*	10,14	6,18	4,8	3,66	-	3,9	3,23
	B027525a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7,38	6,41	10,14	*	3,51	-	-	-	-	-
	B0273279	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,88	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,71	3,92	6,18	3,51	*	3,44	5,2	4,56	-	3,83
	B027108a	-	-	-	-	3,41	-	3,2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,18	3,53	3,95	4,8	-	3,44	*	5,83	4,08	-	4,3
	B027526a	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,07	-	3,66	-	5,2	5,83	*	8,83	-	4,06
B027323a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,56	4,08	8,83	*	4,44	3,13	-	
	B0273249	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,94	3,9	-	-	-	-	4,44	*	-
	B027312a	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,83	4,3	4,06	3,13	-	*	-
	B0273259	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	*

Table 11. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.

Appendix 5 - Table 14

		B027328a	B027569a	B027336a	B027320a	B027333a	B027335a	B0271069	B027527a	B027571a	B0273308	B027568a	B0275729	B027105a	B027338a	B0273349	B027573a	B0273319	B027574a	B027555a	B027326a	B027332a	B027557a	B027329a	B027337a	B027339a	B027341a	B027340a	B027579a	B027580a	B027657a	B0276599	B027672a	B027655a	B027668a			
	B027328a	*	5,81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,53	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	B027569a	5,81	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
B027oak F green main	B027oak F green Gr2	B027336a	-	\	*	7,23	-	-	-	3,13	3,36	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
		B027320a	-	-	7,23	*	5,52	4,7	-	3,45	4,99	3,69	4,06	-	3,41	3,23	3,5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,27	4,22	-	4,48	3,39	3,33	3,94	4,13	-	-	-	-		
		B027333a	-	-	-	5,52	*	7,8	-	-	-	-	3,42	-	-	3,43	3,67	3,46	3,77	3,1	4,86	3,62	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B027335a	-	-	-	4,7	7,8	*	\	3,23	3,55	-	-	-	3,17	4,23	\	-	-	-	4,95	3,4	\	3,53	3,47	-	-	-	3,64	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B0271069	\	\	-	-	-	\	*	8,32	6,21	3,08	-	3,56	-	3,57	-	4,17	3,26	-	-	3,07	-	3,52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B027527a	-	-	3,13	3,45	-	3,23	8,32	*	7,22	3,76	3,35	4,74	-	3,59	-	-	-	3,35	-	3,6	-	4,65	3,45	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B027571a	-	-	3,36	4,99	-	3,55	6,21	7,22	*	6,72	3,23	4,35	-	-	-	-	3,8	-	3,78	-	-	3,6	3,47	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B0273308	-	-	-	3,69	-	-	3,08	3,76	6,72	*	4,48	-	-	-	-	4,78	4,98	-	3,32	3,57	-	4,74	3,76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B027568a	-	-	4,06	3,42	-	-	3,35	3,23	4,48	*	5,31	-	-	-	-	4,97	4,04	4,38	3,77	3,82	3,15	3,29	-	-	-	-	3,61	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,37	-	-
	B0275729	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,56	4,74	4,35	-	5,31	*	-	-	-	-	-	5,06	3,14	3,24	-	4,71	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B027oak F green Gr3	B027105a	-	-	-	3,41	-	3,17	-	-	-	-	-	-	*	5,94	5,91	4,64	3,37	3,52	3,65	-	4,84	-	3,41	-	-	3,1	3,2	-	-	-	3,42	\	-	-	-	
		B027338a	-	-	-	3,23	3,43	4,23	3,57	3,59	-	-	-	-	5,94	*	5,55	5,56	-	3,82	-	-	-	-	3,53	-	-	4,28	3,91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B0273349	-	\	-	3,5	3,67	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,91	5,55	*	5,3	-	3,78	3,08	-	4,26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B027573a	-	\	-	-	3,46	-	4,17	-	-	4,78	4,97	-	4,64	5,56	5,3	*	6,7	5,3	4,06	-	-	3,67	3,47	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
		B0273319	-	\	-	-	3,77	-	3,26	-	3,8	4,98	4,04	-	3,37	-	-	6,7	*	3,9	-	-	-	4,05	3,95	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B027574a	-	\	-	-	3,1	-	-	3,35	-	-	4,38	5,06	3,52	3,82	3,78	5,3	3,9	*	4,39	4,81	-	4,4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,41	-	-	-	-	
	Same tree	B027555a	-	-	-	-	4,86	4,95	-	-	3,78	3,32	3,77	3,14	3,65	-	3,08	4,06	-	4,39	*	3,06	4,14	3,84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		B027326a	-	-	3,59	4,27	3,62	3,4	3,07	3,6	-	3,57	3,82	3,24	-	-	-	-	-	4,81	3,06	*	5,57	3,1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B027332a		\	\	-	4,22	-	\	-	-	-	-	3,15	-	4,84	-	4,26	-	-	-	4,14	5,57	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
B027557a		-	-	-	-	-	3,53	3,52	4,65	3,6	4,74	3,29	4,71	-	-	-	-	3,67	4,05	4,4	3,84	3,1	-	*	3,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B027329a		3,53	-	4,34	4,48	3,03	3,47	-	3,45	3,47	3,76	-	-	3,41	3,53	-	3,47	3,95	-	-	-	-	-	3,01	*	3,02	3,11	3,84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Same tree	B027337a	-	\	-	3,39	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,02	*	22,34	13,61	3,76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B027339a	-	\	-	3,33	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,11	22,34	*	12,48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B027341a	-	-	-	3,94	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,1	4,28	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,84	13,61	12,48	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B027340a	-	\	3,29	4,13	-	3,64	-	-	-	-	3,61	-	3,2	3,91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,76	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B027579a	-	\	-	-	-	-	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Same tree	B027580a	-	-	-	-	-	-	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B027657a	-	-	-	3,05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	B0276599	-	\	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,42	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,64	*	-	-	-	
	B027672a	\	\	\	-	\	\	\	-	\	-	4,37	-	\	-	\	-	\	-	\	-	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	
	B027655a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
B027668a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		

Table 14. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4 bulwarks. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values. AOIFE DALY, Ph.d.

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Appendix 6 – table 20

		B027210a	B027213a	B027311a	B027316a	B027304a	B0271079	B0271039	B027102a	B027315a	B027301a	B027308a	B027310a	B027305a	B027309a	B0275769	B027313a	B027317a	B027303a	B027577a	B027306a	B027307a
B027pine F green It2	B027210a	*	7,51	3,03	-	-	3,31	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,78	3,84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027213a	7,51	*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3,45	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
B027oak F green It2	B027311a	3,03	-	*	-	-	4,16	3,43	-	-	-	3,13	-	3,93	-	-	-	-	-	4,92	3,47	-
	B027316a	-	-	-	*	5,65	3,58	4,36	3,48	-	4,68	-	-	-	-	4,44	-	3,96	4,1	-	-	-
	B027304a	-	-	-	5,65	*	3,39	3,8	4,13	-	4,66	-	-	3,41	3,65	4,12	4,19	3,22	3,72	-	-	-
	B0271079	3,31	-	4,16	3,58	3,39	*	3,99	4,74	4,68	8,01	4,47	3,46	5,06	3,43	-	-	-	-	3,81	4,61	-
	B0271039	-	-	3,43	4,36	3,8	3,99	*	8,54	9,32	6,28	8,84	8,21	4,55	3,34	4,54	-	3,18	4,91	3,65	-	-
	B027102a	-	-	-	3,48	4,13	4,74	8,54	*	18,48	9,96	6,02	7,95	6,61	3,87	4,81	3,77	-	-	3,6	4,69	-
	B027315a	-	-	-	-	-	4,68	9,32	18,48	*	7,39	6,31	7,35	5,26	3,6	4,15	-	-	-	4,49	4,35	-
	B027301a	-	3,45	-	4,68	4,66	8,01	6,28	9,96	7,39	*	5,34	8	3,1	4,56	-	3,27	-	-	4,8	3,56	-
	B027308a	-	-	3,13	-	-	4,47	8,84	6,02	6,31	5,34	*	5,25	5,82	3,2	-	-	-	-	4,38	3,12	-
	B027310a	-	-	-	-	-	3,46	8,21	7,95	7,35	8	5,25	*	-	3,9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	B027305a	3,78	-	3,93	-	3,41	5,06	4,55	6,61	5,26	3,1	5,82	-	*	8,64	6,7	3,75	-	-	3,4	3,62	-
	B027309a	3,84	-	-	-	3,65	3,43	3,34	3,87	3,6	4,56	3,2	3,9	8,64	*	-	3,01	-	-	3,21	-	-
	B0275769	-	-	-	-	4,12	-	4,54	4,81	4,15	-	-	-	6,7	-	*	4,68	-	-	3,14	-	-
	B027313a	-	-	-	4,44	4,19	-	-	3,77	-	3,27	-	-	3,75	3,01	4,68	*	5,35	4,61	3,73	-	-
	B027317a	-	-	-	-	3,22	-	3,18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,35	*	5,64	4,34	-	-
	B027303a	-	-	-	3,96	3,72	-	4,91	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,61	5,64	*	4,55	-	-
	B027577a	-	-	4,92	4,1	-	3,81	3,65	3,6	4,49	4,8	4,38	-	3,4	3,21	3,14	3,73	4,34	4,55	*	3,39	-
B027306a	-	-	3,47	-	-	4,61	-	4,69	4,35	3,56	3,12	-	3,62	-	-	-	-	-	3,39	*	7,66	
B027307a	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7,66	*	

Table 20. Gammel Strand, Copenhagen, Phase 4B land ties. Table showing the correlation (t-test) between each tree-ring curve from this construction phase with each other, at their cross-dated position. Green = oak, orange = pine. The grey tones highlight the high t-values.